

SAPIENZA
UNIVERSITÀ DI ROMA

MASTER DEGREE IN NATURAL SCIENCES

Detectors and Accelerators in Particle Physics

Simulating interactions of photons
and electrons with matter using
Geant4 (Project 05)

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1 Introduction

This practice focuses on the analysis of photon and electron interactions with matter using the Geant4 software. The interaction of 10 GeV electrons and photons with a single block of Aluminium was simulated to reconstruct the spectrum of the fraction of deposited energy in the first $5X_0$. The two spectra, corresponding to electrons and photons, were compared to analyze the differences and similarities between them.

The obtained results were analyzed by comparing the differences when using different physics lists from the available options. Specifically, our focus was directed towards electromagnetic options, namely: default (DEF), EMZ (a slower yet highly accurate option), EMV (a faster but less precise option), EMX (a hybrid combining the characteristics of EMZ and EMV), Livermore, and Penelope. It's worth noting that the Livermore and Penelope options are specifically optimized for low-energy interactions. Additionally, the contribution to the deposited energy of the secondary particles generated during the process was identified.

2 Spectra of the fraction of deposited energy in the first $5X_0$

2.1 Electrons

Figure 1 presents spectra of the fraction of deposited energy in the first $5X_0$ for electrons under different physics lists in Geant4.

(a) With the physics list: DEF

(b) With the physics list: EMV

(c) With the physics list: EMX

(d) With the physics list: EMZ

(e) With the physics list: LIV

(f) With the physics list: PEN

Figure 1: Spectra of the fraction of deposited energy in the first $5X_0$ for electrons using different physics lists.

2.2 Photons

In Figure 2, the spectra illustrating the fraction of deposited energy for photons in the first $5X_0$ are depicted for various physics lists available in Geant4.

2.3 Discussion

2.3.1 Different physics lists

Due to the compatibility of all the results obtained, the EMV physics list has been selected as the preferred choice. This selection was based on its faster computational performance, allowing for more efficient calculations without sacrificing the accuracy and reliability of the obtained results (See Table 1).

Table 1: Fraction of deposited energy under different physics lists for electrons and photons

List	Mean (Electron)	Std Dev (Electron)	Mean (Photon)	Std Dev (Photon)
DEF	0.39	0.11	0.29	0.15
EMV	0.38	0.11	0.29	0.15
EMX	0.39	0.11	0.29	0.16
EMZ	0.39	0.11	0.29	0.12
LIV	0.39	0.11	0.29	0.15
PEN	0.40	0.11	0.30	0.16

(a) With the physics list: DEF

(b) With the physics list: EMV

(c) With the physics list: EMX

(d) With the physics list: EMZ

(e) With the physics list: LIV

(f) With the physics list: PEN

Figure 2: Spectra of the fraction of deposited energy in the first $5X_0$ for photons using different physics lists.

2.3.2 Comparison between the two spectra

Interactions between electrons and photons with matter exhibit fundamental differences. Although both electrons and photons with an energy of 10 GeV initiate electromagnetic showers, the distinction lies in the specific interaction responsible for initiating the shower, where Bremsstrahlung is for electrons, and the pair production is for photons. Hence, our anticipation was that the initiation of the shower would occur at a greater depth for photons compared to electrons and that the fraction of energy deposited within the first $5X_0$ would be greater for electrons than for photons. This phenomenon can be understood by referring to Equation 1.

$$t_{max} = \ln(E/E_c) - C_{e\gamma} \quad (1)$$

$C_{e\gamma} = 0.5$ for photons, and -0.5 for electrons. (t_{max} represents the position in which the maximum amount of energy is deposited within the material). Our simulations indeed exhibit this characteristic behavior, but to validate the results further, it is beneficial to compare them with another simulation conducted using Lead as the absorber material. (See Figure 3).

Figure 3: The fraction of deposited energy (Left: photons, Right: electrons) within the initial $5X_0$ is examined for 10 GeV electrons and photons in a Lead absorber.

The distribution of the energy fraction deposited in the first $5X_0$ by 10 GeV electrons and photons in Lead [1] can be seen in Figure 4. Upon comparing behaviors presented in Figure 3 with Figure 4, a clear and close alignment is observed between our simulations and the results presented in the referenced article. This close agreement provides compelling evidence that our code is functioning properly.

Figure 4: The distribution of the deposited energy fraction within the initial five radiation lengths is examined for 10 GeV electrons and photons in a Lead absorber. Image source: [1]

In addition to that, a peak was observed near zero in the distribution for the photon showers. This is due to the photons penetrating the entire absorber without interacting.

Figure 5: The contribution of secondary particles produced during the interaction process to the deposited energy.

2.3.3 Contribution to the deposited energy of the secondary particles produced

Figure 5 shows the contribution to the deposited energy of the secondary particles produced in the process examined for 10 GeV electrons and photons. Note that the results are presented for the physics list: EMV.

Based on the information presented in Figure 5, it is evident that for electrons, approximately 98.54% of the deposited energy can be attributed to the contribution of secondary particles generated through interactions with the material. In contrast, for photons, this value reaches 100%, indicating that all of the energy deposited by photons is solely due to the presence of secondary particles. This is coherent with the theory since it is anticipated for the primary electron to deposit a fraction of energy via ionization, while the primary photons perform pair production without depositing energy in the material.

References

- [1] Richard Wigmans and Mehmet Tahir Zeyrek. On the differences between calorimetric detection of electrons and photons. *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section A: Accelerators, Spectrometers, Detectors and Associated Equipment*, 485(3):385–398, 2002.